

Online Whiteboard

TOOLSHEET

Purpose

Provide an interactive platform that allows effective online collaboration between multiple consortium partners at the same time. Online whiteboards offer the opportunity to conduct workshops across Europe, co-create content with partners, and build visual overviews in a shared medium.

Benefits

Working effectively together online across Europe proves itself a challenge, but having a shared platform on which multiple consortium partners can work simultaneously can be a tremendous aid. Online whiteboards offer such functionality.

Practical recommendations

Most of the work for both the proposal and the project itself will be done online. It is therefore important to have access to suitable online platforms to collaborate on, and we highly recommend using an online whiteboard application.

While there are professional software applications for these purposes. However, most consortium partners will not have access to such software due to the associated costs. Luckily, there are several good options that offer (limited) free access.

Among others:

- [Miro](#)
- [Mural](#)
- [Klaxoon](#)

These online applications offer a wide range of basic functions for free, especially the first two. Free version of these applications often have limitations to the number of individual whiteboards you can create.

Please note that while there are specialized project support applications out there, such as Mindmaster, the online whiteboard applications generally a good enough not warrant adopting another tool.

The PREMIERE project does not claim ownership of the tools referenced herein; credit belongs to their respective creators.

Applicability box

Main MA Skills supported

Collaboration within an equitable digital co-working space

Relevant Target groups

All

Useful link(s)*

[Miro](#)

[Mural](#)

[Klaxoon](#)

*right click to open

Figure 1: Whiteboard in use for co-creative workshop